
Environmental Communication Discourse in Apple's Mother Nature Campaign Through New Media

Indriyani Dharmaputri¹, Nuryanti², Nana Sutikna³

¹Student, Communication Science Department, Jenderal Soedirman University, Indonesia

^{2,3}Lecturer, Communication Science Department, Jenderal Soedirman University, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study examines Apple Inc.'s Mother Nature campaign, launched in 2023, through Teun A. Van Dijk's critical discourse analysis (CDA). It explores how the company shapes public perceptions and behaviors related to environmental sustainability. By analyzing the campaign's semantic, syntactic, stylistic, and rhetorical elements, the research reveals how Apple uses the figure of Mother Nature to communicate its environmental values and create an emotional connection with its audience. The analysis uncovers the ideological foundations of the campaign, framing Apple's sustainability efforts as both a corporate responsibility and a tool for influencing societal attitudes toward environmental preservation. The macrostructure analysis highlights initiatives in renewable energy, recycling, and carbon reduction. The superstructure analysis explores how the character of Mother Nature challenges the company's environmental impact, positioning Apple as an industry leader. On a microstructural level, the campaign uses informal language, humor, and engaging visuals to make complex environmental issues more accessible. Ultimately, the Mother Nature campaign demonstrates how power, discourse, and environmental ideology intersect in new media. It emphasizes the urgency of addressing climate change through corporate initiatives that align marketing strategies with societal values.

KEYWORDS: Apple, Campaign, Discourse Analysis, Environmental Communication, Van Dijk

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, environmental discourse in Indonesian mass media often does not receive the same level of intensity as political and economic news and is not prioritized as a news topic (Suyanto 2012), [2]. In fact, mass media has the potential to drive change or serve as an agent of social change, particularly in disseminating environmental issues (Gorostidi, Gaston, and Rekondo 2024; Happer and Philo 2013). Despite this, the mass media's role in shaping behavior and culture to preserve the environment remains unreliable. One of the key factors contributing to this issue is that mass media is no longer perceived as an independent entity (Kustiawan et al. 2022; Suyanto 2012).

With the continued evolution of mass media, alternative public spaces, known as new media, have emerged over the past few decades to actively engage with environmental issues. Examples include online news platforms, forums, social media, and more (Putri and Pratiwi 2022). As discussed in (Handayani, Nurapriyanti, and Pratama 2024), mass communication related to human activities is no longer confined to traditional mass media but extends into new media platforms. New media, in its role as an alternative public sphere, is characterized by integration, interactivity, and digitalization (Hapsari 2014).

Among the most frequently discussed environmental issues is climate change. The phrase "Climate change is a fact" has become ubiquitous in both media and everyday life. This phrase underscores the reality that climate change is an immediate threat affecting all living beings on earth (Kakaki 2013; Niñerola, Ferrer-Rullan, and Vidal-Suñé 2020). Climate change can be triggered by natural processes, as explained in the book *Homo Sapiens Rediscovered: The Scientific Revolution Rewriting Our Origins* (Pettitt 2023), which highlights that climate change has posed challenges throughout human evolution, even before the emergence of modern humans. However, a broad consensus among scientists indicates that humans are also a primary contributor to climate change (NASA Global Climate Change 2024). Humanity must now focus on mitigating damage, controlling it, and implementing corrective measures through policies at domestic, national, and global levels to ensure survival (Fatkhullah et al. 2022). Public awareness of climate change is steadily growing. While behavior and lifestyle changes remain limited, there is a noticeable shift in attitudes, with increasing support for climate protection (Venghaus, Henseleit, and Belka 2022). This heightened awareness has prompted corporations, including manufacturers, to prioritize environmental concerns (Hansson and Forssell 2017).

Apple Inc., a leading American multinational technology company, is recognized as the largest manufacturing industry in the world based on its revenue (Mazur 2023; Zhang 2023). As the world's largest company in terms of revenue, Apple has recognized the importance of protecting and investing in the environment as a key determinant of human life in the future. In September 2023,

Environmental Communication Discourse in Apple's Mother Nature Campaign Through New Media

Apple introduced its Mother Nature campaign, which focuses on efforts and various initiatives to produce products using renewable energy and recycled materials, with the goal of achieving carbon neutrality by 2030. The Mother Nature campaign builds upon Apple's ongoing environmental commitment, first introduced on its website in 2020. Moreover, as early as 1990, Apple officially implemented an environmental policy, and in 1991, it began eliminating the use of lead in its batteries.

Apple's campaign products are extensive, including an environmental progress report available on its official website, visual content, and the Mother Nature short film, which has been uploaded to various platforms such as YouTube, X, and Instagram. These platforms play a pivotal role in bridging connections with stakeholders. Nearly all campaign materials feature Apple's vision, mission, values, commitments, and products. The campaign video is published across several platforms, including the company website, YouTube, Instagram, and others. Furthermore, the official website provides detailed information, including the campaign's vision, mission, values, commitments, and a complete transcript. Through this five minute video, Apple seeks to enhance understanding of environmental issues.

The Mother Nature campaign exemplifies a practice in environmental communication. As referenced in the book cited in (Cox 2010) in research (Herutomo and Istiyanto 2021), environmental communication is a subfield within communication studies that integrates several interdisciplinary areas. The two primary functions of environmental communication are: 1) Pragmatic function, encompassing education, alerting, mobilization, and persuasion; and 2) Constitutive function, where language and other symbols shape our perceptions of reality and the nature of environmental challenges.

Based on the above explanation, it is clear that the environmental discourse in new media surrounding the Mother Nature campaign has the capacity to influence audience cognition. According to (Van Dijk 2011) in (Indari and Novianti 2018), the control of audience cognition refers to influencing behavior, norms, ideologies, knowledge, values, and intentions. This study will analyze how environmental communication discourse in the Mother Nature campaign utilizes critical discourse analysis, as outlined by Teun A. Van Dijk. Discourse in mass media, consciously or unconsciously, is influenced by journalists or writers through various factors (Huda, Hidayat, and Alek 2020). Similarly, discourse formed in new media is inevitably shaped by the creators of the campaign. Therefore, this research introduces a sense of novelty in media text analysis by focusing on the rarely explored themes of environmental communication and related issues. The primary objective of this study is to critically examine the interests and ideologies embedded within the campaign.

II. METHODS

The critical paradigm underpins this study due to its foundational emphasis on power relations, systemic inequalities, and the pursuit of social change. Unlike the positivist paradigm, the critical paradigm asserts that social sciences are neither entirely objective nor devoid of values (DeCarlo, Cummings, and Agnelli 2021). The same source emphasizes that research within this paradigm should prioritize and strive for social change. In this context, the researcher examines Apple's Mother Nature campaign in new media as a concrete application of the critical paradigm, focusing on its ability to influence perceptions and catalyze social change.

This study adopts a descriptive qualitative approach, supported by Teun A. Van Dijk's critical discourse analysis (CDA) model, with a particular focus on textual analysis. The researcher will observe scenes and dialogues within the film to produce descriptive data in the form of written texts or descriptions, which will then be linked to environmental communication. According to a journal reference (Wodak 2006), Van Dijk's model also known as the social cognition model, is highly influential in the field of critical discourse analysis. Furthermore, (Wu-Peng 2009) highlights the substantial intersections between communication studies and the concepts of discourse and power, particularly in the analysis of media texts or political discourse analysis. Van Dijk's methodology has also been explicitly recognized as an effective tool for analyzing campaigns (Prawira, Muslikhin, and Riyadh 2024). To establish a foundation for this analysis, Figure 1 illustrates the three fundamental structures of Van Dijk's critical discourse analysis framework.

Figure 1. Van Dijk's Critical Discourse Analysis Model

Environmental Communication Discourse in Apple's Mother Nature Campaign Through New Media

Van Dijk identifies three fundamental structures of discourse: 1) Text; 2) Social Cognition; 3) Social Context. The perspective of text serves to highlight specific points or subjects, which are further divided into three levels, macrostructure, superstructure, and microstructure. The macrostructure refers to the text observed based on the topic or theme presented within it, while the superstructure focuses on the sequence and organization of the text. The microstructure is analyzed through the choice of words and sentence style employed in the text (Maulida Khasanah and Faris 2018; Prawira et al. 2024; Sobur 2006). The microstructure is a core element of text analysis, based on four intrinsic components: 1) Semantics; 2) Syntactic; 3) Stylistics; 4) Rhetoric (Ritonga, Dalimunthe, and Surip 2022). In addition to exploring the text structure as outlined, Van Dijk's model also delves into social cognition and social context, ensuring that all three structures interact and support each other.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Mother Nature campaign, launched in September 2023 on YouTube, garnered 3.8 million viewers within a week of its release and reached 5 million viewers by 2024. This campaign falls under one of the seven areas of environmental communication studies, specifically social marketing and advocacy campaigns. According to (Cox 2010) social marketing and advocacy campaigns encompass initiatives aimed at changing societal behaviors to achieve a desired social or environmental outcome. The campaign is part of Apple's broader communication strategy to demonstrate its commitment to environmental sustainability. In this context, Apple aims to build a positive image among the public and stakeholders. Additionally, its initiatives could inspire other companies in similar industries to adopt similar practices. This underscores that the Mother Nature campaign, focusing on environmental issues, not only enhances the company's image but also has the potential to influence collective behaviors towards sustainability, both within society and among other companies. To better understand how the campaign's messages are structured, a thorough analysis of its textual composition is necessary. The following section provides an analysis of the text using Van Dijk's critical discourse analysis method:

Macrostructure

The Mother Nature campaign centers around Apple's commitment to protecting the Earth while designing its products for 2030. The primary message conveyed is how Apple's efforts and the dedication of its teams work collaboratively to achieve these goals effectively. Information related to Apple's vision, mission, and objectives for 2030 is also communicated through the dialogue in the campaign. Upon deeper analysis, the overall message subtly suggests that Apple, as the world's largest technology company in terms of revenue, is committed to long term environmental preservation.

What sets this campaign apart from others is its unique feature of portraying Octavia Spencer as the character Mother Nature. In her role, she is depicted as a female figure who represents the Earth, interrogating Apple representatives about the tangible actions they have taken to fulfill promises made since 2020. Tim Cook, Apple's CEO, along with other department heads involved in the campaign, represent the company itself. They articulate the company's innovations that have a positive environmental impact, including efforts in materials, clean energy, low carbon shipping, and restoring natural ecosystems.

Superstructure

The critical discourse analysis model by Van Dijk, specifically the superstructure element, focuses on analyzing the narrative structure of the Mother Nature campaign. The analysis examines the schematic elements, including the overall structure of the campaign. The schematic focus extends beyond the sequence of events in the campaign to include the positioning of each message, particularly in terms of when the message is presented or withheld. These stages of the schema are outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. Superstructure Analysis of Apple: Mother Nature

Title	Lead	Story
2030 Status Mother Nature Apple	In 2020, Apple promised to bring its entire carbon footprint to net zero by 2030 through innovations in materials, clean energy, low carbon shipping, and restoring natural ecosystems. Now Mother Nature needs a status report from Apple's environmental team. And it better be good.	In the introduction, the heads of departments at Apple and the CEO are preparing for the arrival of Mother Nature. When Mother Nature arrives at Apple's headquarters, the atmosphere is filled with tension, characterized by overcast skies, thunder, and signs of an impending storm, symbolizing Mother Nature's disappointment. In the body of the campaign, Apple presents its environmental sustainability mission. They focus on various aspects of their commitment, such as eliminating plastic use by the end of 2024, adopting 100% recycled aluminium for production, switching to renewable energy sources like wind and solar power for all Apple

Environmental Communication Discourse in Apple's Mother Nature Campaign Through New Media

		<p>offices, promoting sustainable transportation, reforestation efforts, mangrove forest restoration, and reducing water consumption by 63 billion gallons. Apple summarizes its journey towards becoming a more environmentally friendly brand by 2030. Through this explanation, Mother Nature is surprised by the substantial progress Apple has made in fulfilling its promises before 2030, particularly with the launch of the Apple Watch.</p> <p>The conclusion of the campaign is demonstrated when Apple reaffirms its commitment through the introduction of its latest product, the 100% carbon-neutral Apple Watch 9. As the conversation ends, the sky gradually begins to clear, and the sun breaks through the clouds, symbolizing Mother Nature's satisfaction with Apple's initiatives.</p>
--	--	---

According to Van Dijk's theory, schematic meaning is a strategy used by journalists to support a particular topic by presenting it in a specific narrative sequence, as the schematic flow demonstrates how each section of the text is constructed and organized. Based on the data presented in Table 3, it is evident that at the outset of the campaign, the film director portrays Mother Nature as skeptical of Apple and other companies, viewing them as disappointing. Mother Nature, as a character, serves as an initial point of engagement for the audience. In the middle section, the film director seeks to build public opinion and trust through Apple's environmental initiatives, which also serve as a response from Apple to Mother Nature. Interestingly, the film also directly showcases products as tangible evidence of Apple's actions. Ultimately, Mother Nature is satisfied and entrusts Apple with its mission for 2030 and beyond.

Microstructure

Microstructure analysis is the most in-depth part of Van Dijk's discourse analysis by paying attention to semantics, syntactic, stylistik, and rhetoric (Prawira et al. 2024). A detailed explanation is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Microstructure Analysis of Apple: Mother Nature

Semantics	Findings	Analysis
Background	<p>Mother Nature: The weather was however I wanted it to be. Let's cut to the chase</p> <p>Tim Cook: Since 2020, we've been committed to achieving carbon neutrality. All our offices, stores, and data centers already run on 100% renewable energy.</p> <p>Mother Nature: In 2020, you promised to bring Apple's entire carbon footprint to zero by 2030. Henry David Thoreau over here said, "We have a profound opportunity to build a more sustainable future for the planet we share."</p> <p>Mother Nature: Materials! Status.</p> <p>Woman with iPad: Yes. We are in the process of eliminating all plastic from our packaging by the end...</p> <p>Mother Nature: Let me guess. Fifty years from now when someone else is left holding the bag?</p> <p>Woman with iPad: By the end of next year, actually.</p> <p>Man wearing black: And we're also currently using 100 percent recycled aluminum in the enclosures of all our MacBooks, Apple TVs, and Apple Watch.</p> <p>Man in leather jacket: We're shipping more products by ocean rather than air, which reduces transportation emissions by 95 percent.</p>	<p>The environment is currently plagued by carbon footprints left by various companies, including manufacturing firms. In response to this issue, Apple has committed since 2020 to becoming a fully carbon neutral company by 2030.</p> <p>Apple provides evidence to support its contributions and claims, backed by data since 2020.</p>
Details	<p>Mother Nature: Don't disappoint your mother!</p> <p>Mother Nature: Let me guess. Fifty years from now when someone else is left holding the bag?</p> <p>Woman with iPad: By the end of next year, actually.</p>	<p>Mother Nature desires a net zero carbon footprint earth and the establishment of sustainability for the future through carbon footprint reduction. This</p>

Environmental Communication Discourse in Apple's Mother Nature Campaign Through New Media

		character aims to help the audience emotionally connect with environmental issues. The use of "Mother" emphasizes the emotional bond between humans and the Earth, where she embodies the planet calling on humanity to take responsibility. Additionally, some of her dialogues incorporate elements of comedy, humor, and a relaxed tone.
Aim	Mother Nature: All right. This is my third corporate responsibility gig today, so who wants to disappoint me first?	The carbon footprint is a real threat to the earth and its contents. On the other hand, many companies still don't care about it. Mother Nature, as a representative of the earth inhabited by humans, wants to see the real actions of companies that are unknowingly involved in damaging the environment. The campaign emphasizes the urgency of pro environmental action. The dialogue on the side is a subtle form of satire from Mother Nature towards Apple and other companies that are not considered serious about its promises.
	Man in leather jacket: We're shipping more products by ocean rather than air, which reduces transportation emissions by 95 percent. Lisa Jackson: We've reduced water usage by 63 billion gallons. Mother Nature: I want to see you do more of this. Tim Cook: You will.	Apple strives to inspire audiences to believe in a sustainable future while showcasing the significant progress it has made toward that goal.
Presupposition	Mother Nature: In 2020, you promised to bring Apple's entire carbon footprint to zero by 2030.	Apple has made a commitment to the public in 2020 to achieve a net zero carbon footprint.
Syntactic	Findings	Analysis
Sentence forms	Tim Cook: By 2030, all Apple devices will have a net zero climate impact	The sentence structures used in the campaign tend to be varied, incorporating both inductive and deductive forms. Deductive statements are evident in dialogues that directly convey the primary goal of the campaign. Meanwhile, inductive forms are demonstrated through the presentation of detailed initiatives, such as reducing plastic usage, adopting clean energy, and other efforts that support the campaign's overarching objective.
Coherence		The campaign exhibits a high level of coherence as all elements, theme, narrative, dialogue, and strategy are seamlessly integrated to effectively convey the message of sustainability. The overarching theme of the campaign, Apple's commitment to protecting the planet while designing its products for 2030, is consistently presented throughout each dialogue.
Pronouns	Lisa: We've planted forests Lisa: We've reduced it by 63 billion gallons	"We" is employed by the Apple team to emphasize collective responsibility and teamwork in addressing environmental issues.

Environmental Communication Discourse in Apple's Mother Nature Campaign Through New Media

	<p>Man in orange sweater: Thanks to you and your powerful wind and sun.</p> <p>Mother Nature: I hope we didn't keep you waiting. Mother Nature: I want to see you do more of this.</p> <p>Mother Nature: They all do Mother Nature: They're planting trees.</p>	<p>"You" is frequently used to directly address Mother Nature, symbolizing both the planet and environmentally conscious audiences, fostering a sense of personal engagement.</p> <p>"I", as used by Mother Nature, asserts her authority and position as the embodiment of nature, emphasizing her role as a moral and evaluative force.</p> <p>"They", on the other hand, is used by Mother Nature to critique other parties or companies that have made similar promises but failed to deliver concrete actions, reinforcing Apple's distinction in fulfilling its commitments.</p>
Stylistic	Findings	Analysis
Lexicon	<p>Lisa: Yes. And we've also restored mangroves in Colombia.</p> <p>Mother Nature: What else?</p> <p>Lisa: Grasslands in Kenya.</p> <p>Mother Nature: What's next?</p> <p>Mother Nature's assistant: Electricity.</p> <p>Mother Nature: Electricity. Status.</p> <p>Mother Nature: What's next?</p> <p>Mother Nature's assistant: Transportation</p>	<p>The language style employed in the campaign is designed to influence the audience both emotionally and intellectually. The campaign frequently uses interrogative phrases such as "what else" and "what's next?", repeated multiple times by Mother Nature. This repetition emphasizes the campaign's effort to provoke thought and raise awareness among audiences about the worsening state of the environment due to insufficient environmental consciousness. These rhetorical questions serve as a powerful tool to engage viewers, encouraging them to reflect on their role in addressing environmental challenges.</p>
Rhetoric	Findings	Analysis
	<p>The light in the conference room dims. Members of the team look up. Tim turns to the window. Outside, orchard trees sway from a wind. A cluster of leaves bends in the air. The Rainbow Stage stands bright below a cloudy sky. Back in the conference room, the table rumbles. Water glasses tremble.</p> <p>Mother Nature stares at Tim. He looks back, a serious expression on his face. Mother Nature squints one eye slightly.</p> <p>Mother Nature: OK! Good! See you next year.</p>	<p>Rhetoric is employed to emphasize the meaning or message conveyed within a discourse. In this campaign, the dialogue based discourse is accompanied by Mother Nature's initial cold expression upon entering the room and her later satisfied and happy demeanor upon leaving. These contrasting expressions illustrate the character's initial high level of disappointment, reflecting the need for confirmation from the Apple team. The subsequent expression of relief and comfort, even admiration, signifies her acknowledgment of the initiatives presented by Apple. This progression not only underscores the campaign's message but also enhances its emotional impact on the audience, highlighting Apple's commitment to sustainability.</p>

Based on semantic, syntactic, stylistic, and rhetorical analyses, Apple's Mother Nature campaign showcases highly strategic elements of environmental communication discourse. The campaign not only conveys Apple's sustainability commitment but also constructs a narrative that critiques power dynamics, discourse, and ideology within the context of manufacturing corporations. It

Environmental Communication Discourse in Apple's Mother Nature Campaign Through New Media

is evident that this campaign was crafted with a creative and dialogic approach, incorporating humor to capture audience attention, making it distinct from other campaigns.

IV. CONCLUSION

The campaign utilizes the character of Mother Nature to position Apple as a corporation committed to environmental sustainability while simultaneously fostering an emotional connection with the audience through humor, satire, and the presentation of concrete data and facts. From a critical discourse perspective, the Mother Nature campaign transcends mere environmental messaging, serving as a tool to shape audience perceptions of sustainability, project corporate power, and embed a sustainability ideology aligned with Apple's interests. This strategic combination highlights how new media can function as a complex discursive space where environmental issues, power, and ideology dynamically interact, particularly for Apple as the largest manufacturing corporation by revenue.

REFERENCES

- 1) Cox, J. Robert. 2010. *Environmental Communication and the Public Sphere*. 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications.
- 2) DeCarlo, Matt, Cory Cummings, and Kate Agnelli. 2021. *Graduate Research Methods in Social Work: A Project-Based Approach*. Open Social Work.
- 3) Van Dijk, Teun. A. 2011. *Discourse Studies: A Multidisciplinary Introduction*. 2nd ed. London: Sage Publications Ltd.
- 4) Fatkhullah, Mukhammad, Iwed Mulyani, Armoni Suci Dewi, Muhammad Alhada Fuadilah Habib, and Audina Reihan. 2022. "Strategi Komunikasi Dalam Mengatasi Perubahan Iklim Melalui Pelibatan Masyarakat." *Jurnal Komunikasi Pembangunan* 21(01):17–33. doi: 10.46937/21202341909.
- 5) Gorostidi, Izaro, Andere Ormazabal Gaston, and Guillermo Gurrutxaga Rekondo. 2024. "The Role of Communication Media in Socio-Environmental Conflicts." *Tripodos* (55):02. doi: 10.51698/tripodos.2024.55.02.
- 6) Handayani, Widhia Seni, Tia Nurapriyanti, and Alfian Pratama. 2024. "The Role of Mass Communication in Seeing Ethical and Legal Issues of The Press in The Digital Era (Case Study: The Death of The Press in Greece)." *COMPEDIART* 1(2).
- 7) Hansson, E., and J. Forssell. 2017. "Carbon Footprint Communication : A Study of International Corporations Operating in the Industrial Sector." Thesis, Luleå University of Technology.
- 8) Happer, Catherine, and Greg Philo. 2013. "The Role of the Media in the Construction of Public Belief and Social Change." *Journal of Social and Political Psychology* 1(1):321–36. doi: 10.5964/jspp.v1i1.96.
- 9) Hapsari, D. R. 2014. "Peran Media Baru Dalam Perkembangan Gerakan Sosial." Pp. 223–42 in Boer, Rino F., *Demokrasi dalam Ruang Virtual*. Jakarta: Ikatan Sarjana Komunikasi Indonesia.
- 10) Herutomo, Ch., and S. Bakti Istiyanto. 2021. "KOMUNIKASI LINGKUNGAN DALAM MENGEMBANGKAN KELESTARIAN HUTAN." *WACANA: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Komunikasi* 20(1). doi: 10.32509/wacana.v20i1.1165.
- 11) Huda, Muhammad Faishol Nurul, Didin Nuruddin Hidayat, and Alek. 2020. "An Investigation of Macrostructure, Superstructure, and Microstructure on Online News Text." *NOBEL: Journal of Literature and Language Teaching* 11(2):149–61. doi: 10.15642/NOBEL.2020.11.2.149-161.
- 12) Indari, Anggita Ayu, and Wiwik Novianti. 2018. "Analisis Praktik Wacana Mengenai Kelompok LGBT Dalam Publikasi Daring Feminis." *Journal Acta Diurna* 14(2):156. doi: 10.20884/1.actadiurna.2018.14.2.1359.
- 13) Kakaki, Samaila. 2013. "Climate Change: Its Causes, Effects and Control." *Journal of Educational and Social Research*. doi: 10.5901/jesr.2013.v3n10p73.
- 14) Kustiawan, Winda, H. Erwan Efendi, Kaya Arfah, and Muhammad Zul Akbar Shah. 2022. "INFLUENCE OF MASS MEDIA ON SOCIAL CULTURE OF COMMUNITIES." *INFOKUM* 10(5):254–62.
- 15) Maulida Khasanah, and Faris. 2018. "ANALISIS WACANA KRITIS VAN DIJK PADA TEKS BERITA ONLINE KASUS PENYERANGAN PENYIDIK KPK NOVEL BASWEDAN PADA MEDIA LIPUTAN6.COM PERIODE 11 APRIL 2017 HINGGA 9 APRIL 2018." *JURNAL HERITAGE* 6(2):23–29. doi: 10.35891/heritage.v6i2.1566.
- 16) Mazur, Caitlin. 2023. "The 15 Largest Manufacturing Companies In The World." *Zippia.Com*.
- 17) NASA Global Climate Change. 2024. "Do Scientists Agree on Climate Change?" Retrieved May 12, 2024 (<https://science.nasa.gov/climate-change/faq/do-scientists-agree-on-climate-change/>).
- 18) Niñerola, Angels, Ramon Ferrer-Rullan, and Antoni Vidal-Suñé. 2020. "Climate Change Mitigation: Application of Management Production Philosophies for Energy Saving in Industrial Processes." *Sustainability* 12(2):717. doi: 10.3390/su12020717.
- 19) Pettitt, P. 2023. *Homo Sapiens Rediscovered: The Scientific Revolution Rewriting Our Origins*. London: Thames & Hudson.

Environmental Communication Discourse in Apple's Mother Nature Campaign Through New Media

- 20) Prawira, I., Muslikhin, and M. Riyadh. 2024. "ENVIRONMENTAL COMMUNICATION OF INDONESIAN GOVERNMENT; CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS ON INDONESIAN MINISTRIES SOCIAL MEDIA POSTS." *JWP (Jurnal Wacana Politik)* 9(1).
- 21) Putri, Inda Rizky, and Ellya Pratiwi. 2022. "Aktivisme Digital Dan Pemanfaatan Media Baru Sebagai Pendekatan Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Atas Isu Lingkungan." *Bricolage: Jurnal Magister Ilmu Komunikasi* 8(2):231. doi: 10.30813/bricolage.v8i2.3303.
- 22) Ritonga, Syafriyana, Syairal Fahmi Dalimunthe, and M. Surip. 2022. "ANALISIS WACANA KRITIS MODEL TEUN A. VAN DIJK PADA TEKS BERITA DETIK.COM DAN KOMPAS.COM TENTANG PADATNYA ARUS MUDIK IDUL FITRI 1443 H TAHUN 2022." *Asas: Jurnal Sastra* 11(2):150. doi: 10.24114/ajs.v11i2.37160.
- 23) Sobur, Alex. 2006. *Analisis Teks Media; Suatu Pengantar Untuk Analisis Wacana, Analisis Semiotik, Dan Analisis Framing*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 24) Suyanto. 2012. "JURNALISME DAN LINGKUNGAN HIDUP DI MEDIA MASSA." Pp. 487–92 in *Prosiding Seminar Antarabangsa Ke 5*. Pekanbaru: Repository University of Riau.
- 25) Venghaus, Sandra, Meike Henseleit, and Maria Belka. 2022. "The Impact of Climate Change Awareness on Behavioral Changes in Germany: Changing Minds or Changing Behavior?" *Energy, Sustainability and Society* 12(1):8. doi: 10.1186/s13705-022-00334-8.
- 26) Wijayanto, Xenia Angelica, and Lestari Nurhajati. 2019. "Framing Media Online Atas Pemberitaan Isu Lingkungan Hidup Dalam Upaya Pencapaian Keberhasilan SDGs Indonesia." *LUGAS Jurnal Komunikasi* 3(1):14–23. doi: 10.31334/ljk.v3i1.409.
- 27) Wodak, R. 2006. "Critical Linguistics and Critical Discourse Analysis." in in J. Verschueren and J. Ostman (eds), *Handbook of Pragmatics*. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
- 28) Wu-Peng. 2009. "Book Review: TEUN A. VAN DIJK, *Discourse and Power*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2008. Vii + 303 Pp." *Discourse & Communication* 3(2):222–25. doi: 10.1177/17504813090030020503.
- 29) Zhang, Ruoxi. 2023. "Analysis of Apples Marketing Strategy and Management Model." *Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences* 29(1):24–32. doi: 10.54254/2754-1169/29/20231347.